

Photonic Device Programmability in support of Autonomous Optical Networks

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The emergence and consolidation of increasingly programmable optical devices such as transceivers, amplifiers, multiplexers, or ROADMs - which allow their remote configuration and control by adopting Software Defined Networking principles such as model driven development - is enabling the evolution towards gradually more autonomous networks. Such networks leverage device programmability and are able to adapt and react to traffic and network condition changes, e.g., changing modes of operation or reconfiguring the network state, paving the way for the increased adoption of AI/ML models in support of enhanced network operation.

In this paper, after a short review of some key elements in the control and orchestration systems of optical networks in support of autonomous networking we present in detail a proof-of-concept validation of autonomous, closed-loop dynamic adaptation of transceiver operational modes. This includes: i) the design and development of an SDN agent of a multi-band sliceable bandwidth variable transceiver, based on extended OpenConfig terminal device data models; ii) an SDN controller that performs discovery and management of transceivers' operational modes and maps to Transport API (TAPI) profiles enabling efficient physical layer impairment-aware path computation; iii) a dedicated externalized path computation element / digital twin that performs adaptation recommendations; and iv) an MQTT based telemetry platform for publisher/subscriber based state synchronization between the control plane functional entities to avoid systematic polling.

1. INTRODUCTION

Optical Transport Networks have evolved from carefully planned, statically managed networks towards networks requiring optical programmability and dynamic control. The application of Software Defined Networking (SDN) principles for the control of optical transport networks has been consolidated during the last years, although its development is constantly driven by the need to track new technologies at the data plane level, to efficiently exploit the increasing programmability of network elements/devices, and to address emerging scenarios.

A key enabler technology for 6G networks is multi-band (MB) transmission, which offers increased capacity per fiber by exploiting the S-, E-, O-, and U-bands in addition to C- and/or C+L-bands. MB is very attractive for achieving the required network capacity scaling, as it also maximizes the use of the currently deployed network infrastructure, resulting in reduced CapEx [1]. Similarly, according to the estimations derived from traffic analysis of [2], regional and national nodes should efficiently manage the aggregated traffic, ranging from a few Tb/s in the short term, ten Tb/s in the medium term, and potentially reaching up to a hundred Tb/s in the long term. Other drivers for the adoption of

multiband are capacity scaling the deployment of optical links in support of data center interconnects, cloud storage/computing and on-demand media consumption, notably when reusing the fiber plant is a key cost factor. The diversity in performance characteristics across different frequency bands provides a strategic advantage as transmission can be flexibly adapted to the specific user needs. However, MB transmission also introduces new challenges such as nonlinear effects (i.e., stimulated Raman scattering, SRS) that must be considered within the system design. Specifically, a power transfer between wavelengths with specific spacing occurs because of the interplay of wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) channels across the various bands [3-4]. Finally, different optical amplifiers, filters, modulators, detectors, and lasers should be included according to the operating band. In general, adopting technologies tailored for specific bands, beyond the traditional C-band, are often accompanied by higher implementation costs [5]. In this context, new cost-effective, modular, and scalable transceiver architectures capable of efficiently supporting MB operation become key elements in future 6G networks.

The increased programmability of optical devices, including those being extended to support multi-band transmission and switching, is a

key driver for the adoption of Software Defined Networking (SDN) principles in the control and management of optical networks which, along with flexible optical telemetry platforms, enable more autonomous networks by closing the observe/decide/act loop. Consolidated SDN frameworks based on the model-driven development -- which decouple the transport protocols, data serialization and validation and the actual device data models -- enable a continuous improvement of such data models to cover emerging features such as multiband or multiple operation modes support.

The challenges that an SDN control plane needs to address in this evolution are manifold and they cover: i) architectural aspects, in which monolithic approaches are being replaced by more modular systems with specialized functions (including, for example, externalized path computation); ii) modelling aspects, to cover the modelling of physical layer impairments, node internal architectures and restrictions (e.g, the existence of per-band demultiplexing) and other applicable concepts and iii) algorithmic aspects that are needed to perform resource allocation based on multi-band transmission modelling.

In this paper, an extension of our previous work [6], we start with a summary of our modular, multi-band sliceable bandwidth variable transceiver (S-BVT) and a short review of the adopted SDN framework for the autonomous control of a disaggregated optical network. We present the design, implementation, and validation of the associated SDN agent, including its functional architecture and supported features. After describing the extensions implemented in our SDN control plane for the dynamic adaptation of operational modes based on a digital twin / path computation element, we illustrate how the S-BVT integrates into a provisioning workflow and we provide a proof-of-concept illustrating the overall integrated system.

The SDN control of transceivers has been developed significantly in past years, starting with [7], including the control of advanced devices [8], in automated local restoration [9], or as pluggable interfaces [10] and managing operational modes [11]. The novelty of this paper in this regard is the usage of an extended OpenConfig framework for: i) a *multiband, sliceable* BVT; ii) the support for the operational mode *characterization* in terms of Physical Layer Impairment (PLI) parameters with dynamic discovery; and iii) the integration with an SDN controller that maps such operational mode profiles with north bound Transport application programmable interface API (TAPI) profiles, to be consumed by path validation and computation elements. The conducted proof-of-concept validates the autonomous closed-loop dynamic adaptation of transceiver operational modes. To this end, the SDN controller performs the discovery and management of operational modes and TAPI profiles in support of physical layer impairment aware path computation. Additionally, a dedicated externalized path computation element / digital twin outputs the adaptation recommendations, whilst a MQTT [12] based telemetry platform manages the state synchronization between the control plane functional entities. The latter is chosen leveraging its lightweight and efficient standard messaging protocol. However, similar frameworks can be used such as Kafka [13,14] or Redis [15].

A. Software Defined Networking and Model Driven Development

1. Centralized Control Leveraging Programmability

By adopting a logically centralized control plane model, SDN has most importantly contributed to the consolidation of the network softwarization highlighting both the need for and subsequent adoption of open and standard interfaces. These interfaces enable the

interoperability to support use cases such as dynamic and automated provisioning of data connectivity services.

In the common SDN architectures different models are supported, namely: *integrated, partially disaggregated* and *fully disaggregated*. Macroscopically, the community relies on solid architectural and protocol frameworks, such as NETCONF [16], RESTCONF [17] and more recently gRPC/gNMI [18] along with consolidated service, network, and device data models. Driven by operators' needs [19], SDN has been applied to different optical network deployment models. This includes aggregated/closed systems where proprietary control planes export APIs that enable their operation and integration into overall systems as well.

2. Device Abstraction and Data Model

The success and growth of SDN is in part due to the systematic use of model driven development. This results in an effective approach to design distributed systems for control and management based on the systematic use of data models that can be automatically processed, validated (avoiding repetitive and error prone tasks), and used with optimized transport protocol/s [20]. A recurring challenge is to extend and refine existing models to address additional features and overall evolution of technology. A systematic approach for modelling is required to represent data plane functions and their layering. A common design rule is to develop and consolidate layer/technology agnostic frameworks and concepts and specialize them for specific technologies by means of augmentations. An example of model refinement is related to the need to track advances in optical transmission and switching, tied to device programmability.

B. Autonomous Networking

Fig.1 PoC specific network architecture in support of autonomous networking for the adaptive multi-band S-BVT operational mode use case.

Autonomous networking refers to the process by which the network configures itself based on specific criteria (see Fig.1). Autonomous networks initially rely on a rule-based systems, initially conceived around *Event-Action* tuples. More recently, the adoption of AI/ML trained models such as s Deep Reinforcement Learning appears to be promising. In any case, two clear aspects are required to close the loop: configuration and control, and advanced optical telemetry.

1. Configuration and Control (act)

This aspect refers to the configuration of the data plane, based on the decisions of the control plane. The objective of the configuration and control is to reflect the intent into a given state of the devices configuring

the underlying infrastructure. The existing know-how around the model driven development and data models has provided the framework to configure the devices based on a set of assumptions.

2. Optical Monitoring and Telemetry

Optical monitoring and streaming telemetry are key enablers for advanced functions such as autonomous/autonomic networking via hierarchical and coordinated closed-loops. Streaming Telemetry protocols and architectures such as gRPC/gNMI are increasingly being used to export telemetry data from devices (see [20], and references within). While there is support for event notification and asynchronous processing, new protocols are needed given the need for massive telemetry and state synchronization. Further work is needed to define new functional elements specialized for data collection, aggregation, processing, and policy enforcement. This is clearly tied to the cloudification of the control plane and its decomposition into components that can be developed and integrated independently, allowing the reuse and adoption of Open-Source projects for advanced streaming telemetry, data base support or data visualization.

C. Network Architecture

The addressed use case in this paper is related to the change of the operational mode of the MB S-BVT (i.e., involving aspects such as modulation format or FEC) upon a change in the state and conditions of the network.

Let us describe the network architecture with the help of Fig.1. The optical transport network is composed of a set of Reconfigurable Optical Add/drop Multiplexers (ROADMs) and S-BVTs. The network offers data services between S-BVTs line ports for a given data rate using a Network Media Channel (NMC) characterized by its path and frequency slot (in terms of nominal central frequency and spectrum width). From the point of view of the control plane, a single SDN controller is responsible for the dynamic provisioning of such connectivity services. To this end it exports a North Bound Interface (NBI) that is used by either users (operators) or higher-level orchestrators and translates service requests into per device state configuration. As part of the workflow for service provisioning it may delegate the path computation and/or path validation to a digital twin or path computation engine (PCE). A separate optical monitoring and streaming telemetry platform is deployed to support telemetry data coming from either the devices (for example, per carrier SNR obtained at the receiver or bit-error rate) or from the SDN controller itself that notifies of events taking place in the network. The telemetry platform is based on the usage of the MQTT protocol using the Open Source Mosquitto broker (described later) so telemetry data uses a publisher/subscriber pattern. The collection of telemetry data enables adaptive network operation as a key use case of network automation.

In the Proof of Concept evaluated in Section 5, the proposed topology involves 2 S-BVTs (terminal devices using OpenConfig terminology) with our described prototype in a unidirectional setting and two ROADMs representing the optical line system – these two are emulated at the data plane level due to the lack of actual multiband switching nodes --. The selected topology is considered sufficient to demonstrate the targeted use case. The SDN controller is CTTC implementation that has been extended with multi-band capabilities and with device drivers based on open and standard models. The path computation/digital twin in the scenario is a separate process that uses the TAPI Path Computation data model and uses a basic k-shortest path and first-fit iterative process that computes OSNR accounting for physical linear impairments with different per band effects (for the purposes of demonstrating the closed loop). The agents are implemented using ConfD software properly extended to interact with the device.

Let us note that the SDN controller as well as the SDN agents for the optical devices in the considered scenario are actual implementations using standard and open data models and protocols. These are based on NETCONF/Yang and using either extended OpenConfig (for the operational modes) or OpenROADM device models. Due to the lack of multi-band ROADMs, only the ROADMs are emulated at the data plane level and the S-BVTs are connected using a pair of fibers in a back-to-back setting. From the control plane perspective, the whole scenario corresponds to conditions relatively close to a production environment. The proposed methodology involves setting up a service using the SDN controller North Bound Interface (NBI) to request a service along dynamic channel configuration as detailed in Section 4.C

2. SDN CONTROLLED SLICEABLE BVT

In the scope of ongoing research, we present the development of a S-BVT that follows a modular approach, relying on the usage of a multi-flow aggregator and distributor and including support for MB transport networks.

Fig. 2. Modular S-BVT architecture considering 2 slices based on external modulation and direct detection.

A. Modular design

We propose S-BVTs with a modular and scalable architecture based on a *pay-as-you grow* approach that can exploit multiple technology options, such as direct modulation and external modulation with direct detection (DD) or coherent reception. Here, DD is adopted, at the receiver side, providing a simple and cost-effective approach capable of supporting MB transmission over different paths of a metro aggregation network [5]. This flexible combination of the S-BVT building blocks favors supporting multi-Tb/s network transmission, as demonstrated in [24] and [32]. Generally speaking, the S-BVT supports a variable number of slices and can use different technologies for the aggregator block. In this context, a key objective is to model the different subcomponents and to render the device programmable from the SDN control plane.

The S-BVT encompasses programmable/adaptive multi-carrier (orthogonal frequency division multiplexing, OFDM) and multi-flow transceiver for point-to-point (P2P) / point-to-multipoint (P2MP) supporting 25 GHz flexi-grid channels/flows. Specifically, the proposed S-BVT is based on a set of bandwidth/bit rate variable transceivers (BVTs) that can operate in different bands beyond C-band (i.e. E-, O-, S-, C-, L-, U-bands). Fig. 2, for example, reports an example of an S-BVT with only 2 slices specific implementation based on external modulation with direct detection, but alternative configurations are also possible. In this case, a tunable laser source and a Mach Zehnder modulator (MZM) is considered at each transmitter blocks, operating in the C- and the S-

band, respectively. Furthermore, within the transmitter's DSP block, operations to create a OFDM signal encompass data parallelization, mapping, insertion of training symbols (TS), implementation of the inverse fast Fourier transform (IFFT), insertion of cyclic prefix (CP), serialization, and radio frequency (RF) up-conversion. The OFDM signal is digital-to-analog converted by means of a digital-to-analog converter (DAC). At the receiver side, each slice is photodetected with a PIN photodiode and digital-to-analog converted with an oscilloscope (OSC). The receiver DSP block includes RF down-conversion, data parallelization, CP removal, implementation of fast Fourier transform (FFT), equalization, symbol de-mapping, and serialization tasks. The receiver front-end can also include an amplification and filtering stages adapted to the operating band [4].

A key element of the MB S-BVT is the MB optical aggregator/distributor. This ideally consists of a programmable wavelength spectral switch (WSS), which can operate across multiple bands or either uses a combination of WSSs, each working at a certain band, together with combiners/splitters or other passive solutions. A more static and lower cost solution can be based on the adoption of passive optical filters, such as band pass filters (BPFs), at the expense of losing transceiver flexibility and scalability. To address cost and power efficiency constraints, the usage of programmable PIC-based WSS solution is envisioned, thanks to the evolution of the related technology making this approach promising for future networks [6], [22], [23].

One of the goals in this work is to characterize and model transmission effects in the S-band and, accordingly, devices supporting the S-band were acquired for the transceiver prototype. Given the modular architecture of the S-BVT, nothing prevents the L-band being used, provided that the required devices (tunable laser source, filters, amplifiers, and multi-band aggregator/distributor) supporting that band are available.

B. Multi-band support

Two independent BVTs, conforming the S-BVT, have been enabled operating in the S- and C-bands, respectively. The MB S-BVT supports tunable sources covering the C- and S- bands (work is ongoing to include the L band), as shown in Fig. 3. So, each laser wavelength can be properly configured to operate in a particular band. Then, a high-capacity flow is created and distributed by means of a MB optical aggregator and distributor, which are based on BPFs. Multi-band operation is supported by adopting key technology in each S-BVT building block adapted for a particular band (i.e. TLS, filters, amplifiers) and an optical aggregator/distributor capable of supporting MB operation.

Regarding the development of the proposed S-BVT, different conditions, parameters and operational modes have been considered including: i) band selection by determining the range of wavelengths for operation in the S- and C-bands that the different transceiver devices/elements can support, ii) optical aggregator/distributor design capable to support S+C operation; iii) transmitter and receiver front-end configuration/selection to support MB assessment within a metro network scenario while reducing simplicity and cost-efficiency and iv) filter and amplification technology capable to support a particular band operation.

Finally, the development of the S-BVT also faces some challenges related to the increased complexity/cost when operating in different bands beyond the conventional C-band. Additionally, the use of a programmable filter, such as WSS, for the development of the optical aggregator/distributor devices is still low mature technology for operation in bands beyond the C-band. The adoption of static filters, BPFs, are suitable options however at the expense of reduced flexibility/performance. The agent allows specifying either a common

operational mode for both optical bands or operational modes that are specific for each band [33].

Fig. 3 Optical spectrum of the S-BVT transmitting in the C- band (left) and in the S- band (right).

3. SDN AGENT DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

To enable remote programmability, the control and management functions of a device expose an API towards external applications or clients. A domain SDN controller behaves as a client. NETCONF/YANG are an industry-wide adopted transport protocol and data modeling language. A common approach to implement an SDN agent is to decompose it into two main functional blocks: a front-end, able to support NETCONF/yang, and a back-end, which is responsible for the actual device configuration using internal interfaces. The architecture of our implemented agent encompasses a front-end and a hardware abstraction layer (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Functional architecture of the SDN agent for S-BVT, using the ConfD framework and agent logic process for the MB S-BVT.

A. ConfD-based NETCONF front-end

The front-end relies on the ConfD framework [26]. ConfD is a framework for the development of device control and management systems (i.e., *SDN agents*) for networking equipment, and supports several northbound interfaces (e.g., NETCONF). It provides required features such as transaction management, high availability, security, and role-based access control. ConfD provides full NETCONF support

including support for transactions, validations, confirmed commits, rollbacks, event notifications, partial locking, and XPath filtering. These capabilities enable the SDN controller to use advanced filtering and data selection rather than having to retrieve big sections of the data model for local parsing with significant bandwidth savings. ConfD transaction management allows defining two-phase commit transactions ensuring a consistent state.

ConfD supports parsing of and precompiling YANG data models including the generation of source files in support of the development of the *Hardware Abstraction Layer (HAL)*. The HAL term refers to the software that interacts with the device using low level interfaces. The HAL extends the agent's behavior based on changes on the NETCONF datastore(s), and maps changes in the datastore to device configuration being device-specific.

B. OpenConfig data model framework

Open Optical Terminals in general cover transponders, switchponders, muxponders, etc. with the ability to switch and multiplex multiple client signals into optical signals. The agent deals with uniform components hierarchy, multiplexing stages and cross-connection logic discovery and optical channel configuration comprising Frequency, power, and operational mode. We followed the OpenConfig [25] framework for the S-BVT, reusing the existing approach to model an optical platform and terminal device. Our current work focuses on two different operations within the OpenConfig data model: (a) optical channel configuration, and (b) logical channel assignment. The first operation addresses the configuration of an optical channel with a particular central frequency, power, and *operational mode*. To do this, we extended the underlying YANG model to support the dynamic configuration of the optical channels (i.e., central frequency) of the different slices, in other words, multiple optical channels in a single line port.

Let us note that the operational mode field was, originally, vendor-specific and encodes the different transmission modes supported by the device/transceiver into a single integer value. The corresponding value can specify information about the transmission/signals such as modulation format, or FEC.

C. Hardware Abstraction Layer

The actual logic is implemented as a second process that connects to the ConfD daemon via dedicated sockets and implements different

classes for interacting with the ConfD engine. MAAPI is a C API which provides full access to the ConfD internal transaction engine. The CDB API can read (committed) configuration from the CDB and has functions for operational (state) data only. With MAAPI, it is possible to create or attach to existing transaction and access configuration data in the CDB. The modifications are then propagated at commit time of the transaction. Notably, the HAL addresses notification of changes in the configuration database, registering for appropriate call-backs for changes in the configuration of optical channels. This includes the actual frequency, the transmit optical power, and the operational mode. The configuration process relies on the CDB API and MAAPI from ConfD to write on the operational data store, in such a way that operational data can be written to the ConfD database based on the status of the hardware.

D. Optical Channel Configuration

The configuration of the optical channel (per slice) can include the configuration of the power and central wavelength of the tunable laser sources and DAC/ADC channels conforming each BVT/building block of the MB S-BVT.

E. OpenConfig Operational Mode Profiles

Characterizing OpenConfig operational modes is done by means of a profile, that specifies a set of attributes. We have implemented this extension and thus, operational modes can be dynamically retrieved. By adopting a vendor-neutral data model, a single SDN agent can be implemented for each MB S-BVT focusing on wide transmission features, commonly considered by network operators.

Recently, an extension of the OpenConfig data model addresses the full characterization of the operational mode capabilities to enhance optical terminal devices management and remove ambiguity. Such an OpenConfig model extension covers both *standard* operational modes, that is, those defined by ITU-T, with existing external references, and *explicit* operational modes. In explicit modes, various parameters characterizing the mode are explicitly listed. These operational mode capabilities include the modulation format, bit rate, baud rate, optical channel spectrum width, min Tx/Rx OSNR min and max input power, max CD or max DGD, and FEC characterization (i.e., coding, coding overhead, coding gain, or pre-FEC BER threshold).

4. SDN CONTROLLER EXTENSIONS

Fig.5. Validation scenario with 4 nodes (2 S-BVT/terminals, 2 OpenROADM emulated nodes)

Finding a feasible path in the network is a fundamental function in an SDN controller. With MB transmission and switching, along with the increased data rates, efficient path computation requires accounting for the effect of PLI for QoT estimation and validation. This has several implications: i) it is critical to characterize the operational modes of the device reflecting its attributes; ii) topological details in the data models should include PLI; and iii) it is worth considering the benefits of externalizing the computation and validation to specialized and dedicated path computation engines [27], e.g., GNPpy [31]. To leverage the benefits of the OpenConfig operational mode capabilities, such information needs to be available to those external entities. This is the scope of the recently added TAPI profiles in the controller NBI.

A. Transport API Profiles

The ONF Transport API working group has defined the concept of TAPI profile [28]. Profiles provide static, invariant data that groups and centralizes related information and that can be referred to by other TAPI objects, thus avoiding unnecessary duplication. To this end, the TAPI context, between a TAPI client and TAPI server has been extended to include a list of profiles. Specific per-model augmentations provide details on a given profile type. TAPI Node Edge Points (NEPs) – TAPI terminology to refer to the topological aspect of network element physical or logical ports) can refer to *transmission capability profiles*, including the potential payload structure. In the photonic media context, transceiver profiles can be either standard or explicit. See [28] for additional details on the transceiver profiles. The SDN controller maps operational mode details (obtained from the Terminal using the controller South Bound Interface, SBI) into transceiver profiles. By extending the TAPI context, externalized path computation elements may retrieve the list of supported profiles (associated to underlying OpenConfig operational modes) and execute an effective RSA computation, as in [30].

Fig.6. Initial synchronization and discovery upon S-BVT device onboarding, including operational modes capabilities.

B. Externalized Path Computation Element

The purpose of the paper is to demonstrate the network automation and closed loop involving SDN, telemetry and dynamic adaptation/operation of the S-BVT. That said, in multi-band scenarios, path computation is a critical function. In this work, given the simplicity of the used topology, the path computation here uses a simple heuristic

based on a simple multiband transmission modelling accounting for OSNR estimation based on reach and is based on k-shortest path with continuity constraint and first fit iterating the available bands. More complex path computation elements can be based on advanced heuristics as in [27] or using well-proven approaches like GNPpy [31].

The PCE/DT performs path computation and validation and recommends re-routing actions upon a certain event, such as over-exceeding a defined monitoring threshold. The network state, used as input data, is gathered by means of asynchronous TAPI Streaming Telemetry (see Section 5.E) rather than adopting a polling mechanism. This entity also retrieves MQTT information from the data plane devices to decide triggering either a rerouting or capacity adjustment action.

C. Service Provisioning Workflow

As part of the discovery and onboarding process, the SDN controller connects to the SDN agents following the procedures of the used protocol. In NETCONF, after a successful SSH session establishment requesting the Netconf subsystem, HELLO messages are exchanged describing the supported capabilities (see Fig. 6). In this work, this discovery process is augmented to retrieve the operational modes and their PLI characterization.

Fig.7 Streaming based synchronization and Service provisioning process followed by a reroute indication.

The usage of an externalized PCE/DT requires the shared databases between the SDN controller and the PCE to be synchronized. This is commonly accomplished by systematic polling. However, a more effective approach, adopted in this work, involves the usage of a Streaming Telemetry Platform. We have implemented clients for either Redis, Kafka or MQTT, and use TAPI Streaming [29] to notify about changes in the network state. This allows an asynchronous and more robust synchronization and does not negatively affect path computation latency due to synchronous TAPI context retrieval as done via polling approach [27]. The service provisioning, illustrated in Fig. 7, starts with the end user requesting a connectivity service via the controller NBI. The SDN controller needs firstly to identify the involved endpoints by mapping the involved Service Interface Points (SIPs). Then, assuming an externalized PCE/DT, the request is forwarded to the path computation engine, which provides the path attributes including the operational mode to be used at the S-BVT. As commented above, if network conditions change, the PCE/DT may autonomously instruct the controller to change the operational mode and/or reroute the connection.

In this sense, the dynamic configuration of the channel at the provisioning time mainly involves the configuration of the OpenROADM devices and the OpenConfig transceivers. In the former, a sequence of Netconf operations in which, assuming the Optical Transmission Section (OTS) and the Optical Multiplex Section (OMS) Trail Termination Point (TTP) interfaces are pre-configured, the Media Channel (MC) TTP and the Network Media Channel (NMC) Connection Termination Point (CTP) interfaces as well as a roadm-connection object referring to the CTPs for that media channel are instantiated to setup a cross-connection. For the latter, a Netconf edit-config message is sent specifying the frequency power and operational mode for the optical channel in the device.

Upon a network state change detected by the telemetry system and notified to the SDN controller via MQTT, the dynamic (re)configuration can involve multiple options: a full reroute, in which a new path and frequency slot (media channel) is allocated and enforced using a break-before-make approach (which requires a deletion and a creation using the aforementioned workflow); a change in transmission power (only requires a new OpenConfig edit-config message in the optical channel) or a change in the central frequency (which is implemented similarly to a reroute). For operations that – without change in the media channel – only involve the Tx, it is also theoretically possible to change the operational mode which, in our prototype – would mean a change in the modulation format by changing the DSP, e.g., applying different modulations per carrier based on the carriers' SNR.

5. PROOF of CONCEPT AND VALIDATION

This section presents the validation of the SDN-controlled, sliceable, MB bandwidth variable transceiver, in a fully disaggregated network scenario depicted in Fig.5. The validation covers the management of S-BVT operational modes across the whole provisioning process workflow. We demonstrate the retrieval of the operational modes, how they are mapped to TAPI transceiver profiles, and later used for path computation/validation and the subsequent configuration of the BVT, including closed-loop adaptive transmission use cases.

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</state>
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<state>
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SDN Controller http://10.1.1.150:4900/restconf

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name {3}
operational-modes {0}
profile [1]
▼ 0 {3}
  uuid : e49affb1-6d73-5a6e-a3fb-1b90f576f9f3
  profile-type : tapi-photonic-media:PHOT_PROFILE_TYPE_TRANSCEI
  tapi-photonic-media:transceiver-profile {1}
  ▼ transceiver-explicit-profile {2}
    ▼ common-organizational-explicit {5}
      ► frequency_range {2}
        tx-channel-power-min : 0.0
        tx-channel-power-max : 25.0
        rx-channel-power-min : 0.0
        rx-channel-power-max : 9.0
    ▼ common-explicit {11}
      line-coding-bitrate : TRIB_RATE_40G
      max-chromatic-dispersion : 200.0
      max-diff-group-delay : 1.0
    ▼ chromatic-and-polarization-dispersion-penalty [2]
      ▼ 0 {3}
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        chromatic-dispersion : 800.0
        penalty : 10.0
      ▼ 1 {3}
        index : 1
        chromatic-dispersion : 0.77
        penalty : 1.0
    ▼ max-polarization-dependent-loss-penalty [1]
      ▼ 0 {3}
```

Fig. 8. OpenConfig operational mode capabilities (up) and mapping to the NBI TAPI Transceiver Profile (bottom) – selected data nodes.

A. FlexOpt SDN controller

The CTTC *FlexOpt* SDN controller targets the control and management of partial or fully disaggregated optical networks. Such a controller may be deployed as an optical controller, including the configuration and control of OpenConfig-enabled transceivers and ROADMs, or as an optical line system (OLS) controller in a partial disaggregated scenario. As an SDN controller, it provides connectivity services between transceiver line ports. As an OLS controller, it is responsible for providing a path (photonic media channel) between the line side ports of the transponders (or, equivalently, from the ROADM add/drop ports).

The RESTCONF server processes requests using the RESTCONF protocol. Currently, the supported YANG models are a subset of the ONF TAPI v2.1. Requests are mapped to internal structures and processed by functions in the event manager. In particular, the SDN controller provides dynamic connectivity services covering the Digital Signal Rate (DSR) and PHOTONIC MEDIA layers. The controller is configured with the IP address and credentials of the devices. After an initial NETCONF Hello, the SDN controller moves to the discovery phase, starting with the capability exchange. This permits the SDN controller checking the presence of the SDN agent capability that manifests support for operational modes (<capability><http://example.net/yang/openconfig-terminal-device-property-types?module=openconfig-terminal-device-property-types> in our case), and proceeds to retrieve the device component structure. It sends a NETCONF <get> for <components xmlns='http://openconfig.net/yang/platform'/> and the terminal device data by means of a <get> for <terminal-device xmlns='http://openconfig.net/yang/terminal-device'/>.

Part of this discovery process involves the identification of optical channels and their current configuration. The SDN controller receives

the list of supportable operational modes and may proceed to obtain the different properties of each mode. Our S-BVT lists, for example, mode 100 as potentially usable mode (see Fig. 8). This is later mapped to TAPI transceiver profiles. Once the operational modes are discovered, the SDN controller adds the transceiver profiles to the TAPI context. Fig. 8 shows the resulting TAPI Transceiver profile that is exported to, for example, Operation Support Systems (OSS), higher functional entities, SDN clients or path computation elements. In parallel, the SDN agent HAL subscribes to the event associated with the following data model YANG nodes (with OpenConfig convention of grouping configuration aspects in ./config trees sibling to ./state trees):

```

./terminal-device/logical-channels/channel/config
./terminal-device/logical-channels/channel/logical-channel-
assignments/assignment/config
./components/component/oc-opt-term:optical-channel/config

```

```

{
  "service": {
    "layer-protocol-name": "TAPI-Path-Computation",
    "layer-protocol-qualifier": "Output",
    "end-point": {
      "end-point": "TAPI-Path-Computation:Output:Service:End-Point"
    }
  },
  "path": {
    "link": {
      "topology-uuid": "TAPI-Path-Computation:Output:Service:Path:Link",
      "link-uuid": "TAPI-Path-Computation:Output:Service:Path:Link"
    },
    "mc-pool": {
      "available-spectrum": "TAPI-Path-Computation:Output:Service:Path:Mc-Pool"
    }
  },
  "operational-mode": {
    "operational-mode": "100"
  }
}

```

Fig.9 TAPI Path Computation message between the SDN controller and the PCE/DT showing the computed path along with the selected operational mode (retrieved via asynchronous TAPI telemetry).

B. Path Computation Element

As part of the provisioning workflow, the PCE/DT performs path computation and validation and recommends re-routing actions upon a certain event (e.g., monitoring threshold). Recall that here, the network state is synchronized by means of asynchronous TAPI Streaming Telemetry. Fig. 9 shows the path computation exchange between the SDN controller and the PCE/DT, including the allocation of the frequency slot and the operational mode. The path computation exchange took 14 ms $\sim O(10\text{ms})$. The PCE/DT assigned the operational mode and the central frequency to be configured in the S-BVT.

C. S-BVT SDN agent

A docker container includes an instance of the *ConfD* daemon (version 8.0.9) that is responsible for NETCONF/YANG remote access to the configuration database. A second container includes a process that connects to the *ConfD* server as explained above. The target validations cover: i) the startup of the *ConfD* daemon and loading of initial operational and configuration data; ii) the -retrieval of the datastore of

the NETCONF agent; iii) the retrieval of components of the OpenConfig terminal device, including focusing on the optical channel augment; iv) the retrieval of the characteristics and current state of an optical channel component; and v) the dynamic configuration of an optical channel attributes.

1. Agent start-up and initial onboarding and discovery

The *Instantiation Delay* characterizes aspects related to the instantiation of the agent's containers, and/or memory usage. Launching the *ConfD* framework, which includes the loading of the operational and initial configuration data, can range from $\sim 17 - 20$ ms (lower bound when operational data and config data are pre-stored in xml files) to several seconds (1.230 s in a sample execution). This is due to the latency to retrieve operational data from the devices. The HAL startup time is ~ 8 ms, including subscription to events. Consequently, including the container orchestration latency, the initial startup of the SDN agent is characterized by $O(10\text{s})$.

```

<get>
  <filter type='subtree'>
    <name>OCH-A-Out-1</name>
    <operational-modes
      xmlns='http://example.net/yang/openconfig-
terminal-device-properties'>
      <mode-descriptor>
        <mode-id>100</mode-id>
      </mode-descriptor>
    </operational-modes >
  </filter>
</get>

```

Fig.10 NETCONF get message including a filter to retrieve the details of a specific operational mode (mode-id 100).

The *Discovery latency* is defined as the time of the SDN controller to discover the components of the transceiver upon a NETCONF get operation. This latency comprises the time and the control plane overhead (in terms of bytes, and throughput). With a back-to-back setting between the controller and the agent, the retrieval of components is done in ~ 475 ms (for an equivalent of ~ 400 xml lines). Similarly, the *Operational Mode Characterization latency* is the time to obtain the parameters of a given operational mode given its mode-id (see Fig. 10). The retrieval of the operational mode took ~ 300 ms, associated to a NETCONF reply with 84 XML lines (4837 characters).

2. Channel Configuration and client assignment

The basic operation of channel configuration (a) involves sending an edit-config operation to modify YANG leaves associated to the parameters of the optical channel component, as shown in Fig. 11.

```

<components xmlns='http://openconfig.net/yang/platform' >
  <component operation='merge' >
    <name>OCH-A-Out-1</name>
    <oc-opt-term:optical-channel
      xmlns:oc-opt-term=
'http://openconfig.net/yang/terminal-device' >
    <oc-opt-term:config>
      <oc-opt-term:frequency>195300000
        </oc-opt-term:frequency>
      <oc-opt-term:target-output-power>4
        </oc-opt-term:target-output-power>
      <oc-opt-term:operational-mode>100
        </oc-opt-term:operational-mode>
    </oc-opt-term:config>
    </oc-opt-term:optical-channel>
  </component>
</components>

```

Fig.11 NETCONF edit-config message to set the details of a specific Optical channel including operational mode.

The second operation (b) assigns a client port to an optical channel to establish a connection between two transceivers/terminal devices. The actual workflow involves different operations, described below.

At the transmitter side, the central frequency and power of the Tunable Laser Source (TLS) and the Digital/Analog Converter (DAC) channels are modified. At the receiver side, the OSC can be reconfigured. For example, two transceiver slices of the S-BVT1, working within C- and S-bands and corresponding to two different clients (c1 and c2), and two receiver slices of the S-BVT2 are configured. This operation determines different parameters, such as frequency (e.g., 193.4 THz, 200.26 THz), operational-mode (e.g., 111), name (e.g., OCH-A-Out-1, OCH-A-Out-2), power (e.g., 6.5 dBm, 4 dBm), status (e.g., enabled, disabled), type (e.g., optical-channel) and direction (e.g., TX, RX). Note that in this case, the power at S band is lower being constrained by laser stability.

A total setup time of ~300s is needed to perform all the required OpenConfig operations to set up the connection. This time is mainly caused by the programmable elements of the MB S-BVT1, which include the TLS and the DAC, and are eventually configured within ~60s. On the other hand, the configuration of the MB S-BVT2 requires a higher setup time around 254s. The reason behind this is the time needed to configure the oscilloscope, which acts as ADC and includes both the signal acquisition and SNR/BER calculation (offline DSP).

Time	Source	Destination	Protocol	Length	Info
5693	localhost	localhost	MQTT	138	Connect Command
5695	0.800019967	localhost	MQTT	87	Subscribe Request (id=1) [tapi/streaming]
5699	0.800153628	localhost	MQTT	78	Connect Ack
5701	0.800189926	localhost	MQTT	71	Subscribe Ack (id=1)
5703	0.800213119	localhost	MQTT	71	Subscribe Ack (id=2)
7115	5.499247567	localhost	MQTT	12088	Publish Message [tapi/streaming]
7121	5.499267609	localhost	MQTT	12088	Publish Message [tapi/streaming]
7138	5.49437652	localhost	MQTT	12088	Publish Message [tapi/streaming]
7145	5.495111234	localhost	MQTT	12088	Publish Message [tapi/streaming]
7237	5.877166538	localhost	MQTT	5957	Publish Message [tapi/streaming]
7238	5.877258521	localhost	MQTT	5957	Publish Message [tapi/streaming]
7249	5.884425731	localhost	MQTT	5145	Publish Message [tapi/streaming]
7241	5.884593996	localhost	MQTT	5145	Publish Message [tapi/streaming]
7242	5.885422789	localhost	MQTT	1437	Publish Message [tapi/streaming]
7243	5.885489344	localhost	MQTT	1437	Publish Message [tapi/streaming]
7244	5.885654965	localhost	MQTT	2115	Publish Message [tapi/streaming]

Fig.12. Wireshark capture of the initial MQTT synchronization from the SDN Controller to the MQTT broker (collocated in localhost).

E. Streaming Telemetry

We use MQTT as a streaming platform where a MQTT intermediate broker forwards publications in topics to subscribers. This enables synchronizing the FlexOpt SDN controller (publisher) with the PCE/DT functional element (subscriber). The latter connects to the Mosquitto MQTT broker and subscribes to [tapi/streaming] topic to receive asynchronous notifications. The initial synchronization happens at startup, after the network has been discovered which takes O(6s), namely: 5 seconds for network discovery (with the corresponding OpenConfig and OpenROADM messages), and around 900 ms involving the sending of ~40 MQTT publish messages. The initial synchronization

forwards to the PCE/DT relevant information, such as network topology and supported operational modes as reflected in Fig. 12.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This work has illustrated a use case of network automation exploiting hardware programmability in closed loop scenarios, addressing the dynamic adaptation of transceivers operational modes. There are significant gains in terms of automation and towards truly autonomous networking. This requires refinement of existing control and orchestration architectures to natively support optical monitoring and telemetry in a scalable way. In particular, this work has presented the design and implementation of an SDN controlled S-BVT, with multiband capabilities, focusing on the SDN agent implementation and the operational mode characterization and its integration in a control plane. We have shown the integrated retrieval of OpenConfig operational mode profiles from the device, their mapping to TAPI profiles and the consumption by means of externalized path computation elements and Digital Twins. This shows the importance of inter-SDO alignment in terms of data models, avoiding mapping or interworking issues.

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